

Description:

Conversations Toward Solutions workshops were an extension of the Insights to Inspire program. These workshops were designed to explore the experiences and challenges hubs faced with common data issues across the consortium.

Many hubs experience common problems and each hub has established ways of dealing with that problem. This was an opportunity to learn from one another through mutual engagement, to have conversations about how we've addressed problems in our respective institutions, to talk about pros and cons, and to discuss strategies about how we might address these common issues.

The facilitated 60-90 minute workshops were open to anyone in the consortium wishing to join the conversation. Following each workshop, a summary report was distributed for those who couldn't attend, so that they could benefit from the insights of their peers.

The specific topics for discussion were:

- Access to Electronic Health Records
- Researcher Informatics
- Health Information Exchanges

This document includes the summaries from each of the workshops.

Workshop Summary for Access to Electronic Health Records Workshop

August 15, 2022

Collaborators:

Moellner A, Olex A, Nguyen A, Walden A, Solomonides A, Knosp B, Ostasiewski B, Laraway B, Roper C, Land C, Alexander C, Porter C, Willett D, Davis H, Lansky H, Otado J, Higgins J, Brown J, Holden-Wiltse J, Grudzinski J, McKenzie J, Obeid J, Kirsch J, Ciesinski K, Tranelli K, Miller K, Gersing K, Rodgers L, Abajian M, Haendel M, Adibuzzaman M, Elkin P, Shankar P, Paranal R, Burks S, Casey S, Kinzy S, Patterson S, Rojevsky S, Harper T, Farquharson T, Lins T, Campion T, Pauli T, Huerta T, Meadows W, Greer Z

Workshop Facilitator: Timothy Huerta, PHD, MS, Director, Biomedical Informatics, The Center for Clinical and Translational Services (CCTS) Chief Research Information Office (CRIO) and Associate Dean of Research Information Technology Professor, Biomedical Informatics and Family and Community Practice

Number of attendees: 47

Number of unique hubs attending: 23 hubs and 1 NCATS representative

Hub size of unique hubs: Small = 9, Medium = 3, Large = 9, Unsure = 2

Years of experience in Informatics of attendees: average years = 10.87 and range = 0-39 years

Summary:

The goal of the Conversations Toward Solutions workshop was to give individuals a platform to discuss their challenges and experiences with access to electronic health records. The experiences shared by the attendees were analyzed to identify common themes, which included: access, resources, training/knowledge/skill, workflow, and data literacy.

The workflows developed by institutions to ensure data security are also a barrier to providing access in a timely and efficient manner. The person or department that approves access is not necessarily the entity that provides the access. In addition, those requesting access may not know what they need or may not have a “clear research question”. These two obstacles contribute to the delay in accessing EHR data.

Training was mentioned as a concern in several of the use cases discussed during the workshop. Examples included the need for training to understand EHR data, chart review guidelines, and use of the Epic system. A few institutions require annual completion of human subjects and HIPAA Privacy and Security training. Attendees indicated that it’s possible that individuals at their institutions may not be aware of the training opportunities available to them.

An overarching theme from the workshop was a lack of data literacy and resources. Researchers may not understand the EHR data and need analysts to assist them and many do not have this resource. As one attendee stated, “Access to the EMR doesn’t convey understanding of the information or ability to navigate the EMR.”

Appendix 1 includes all comments made on the Miro boards during the workshop. Appendix 2 includes the question and answer session of the workshop.

Suggestions for improving the session format:

- *This format was excellent*
- *Liked the format - I agree it is a way to engage other voices*
- *I think the format is good, but, have to discuss one scenario!*
- *A little chaotic at the start, but once I figured out the platform it worked great, so appreciated the time to acclimate. This is a great format for an interactive workshop!*
- *A bit confusing. Hard to see other people's comments.*
- *Like this format too! Short of an in person meeting, fosters interaction in a larger group, which is hard to do virtually. I learned a bunch*
- *Was expecting a webinar, got a workshop, and the format was helpful.*
- *Not sure that this format is easily accessible for people with visual disabilities. Is there another way to use these tools in ways that are more accessible?*

Participating Hubs:

- Georgetown University
- Johns Hopkins University
- Medical University of South Carolina
- Ohio State University
- Oregon Health & Science University
- State University of New York at Buffalo
- Tufts University
- University of California - Davis
- University of Colorado Denver
- University of Iowa
- University of Kentucky
- University of Michigan
- University of Southern California
- University of Texas Galveston
- University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center
- University of Virginia
- University of Wisconsin Madison
- University of Chicago Department of Medicine
- University of Rochester
- Virginia Commonwealth University
- Wake Forest University
- Washington University
- Weill Medical College

Appendix 1: Comments from Use Case Discussions

For this workshop, addressing each of the Use Case scenarios, please discuss the processes, challenges and barriers to providing researchers interactive access to your organization’s Health Record System?

Use Case 1: You have a PI without access to your EHR who is approved by the IRB to conduct a chart review.

If have access to Epic, then Slicer Dicer is one tool, but not all researchers have this. Have i2b2 and TriNetX as other options for all researchers.
PI may have IRB permission to gain access to certain patient records, but access is brokered through our informatics team.
Process: brokered access. Issues: EHR (data warehouse) data analyst bandwidth issues.
PIs are often too busy to fully understand the process
Privacy Regulatory to gain direct access- UK
PIs may not be aware of how to access the Data
PIs may not have the tools to use the data or the analysis people to look at the data
Go to the BMI Investigator and ask your question of the data. UB
PIs may not be aware of how to access the Data
The PI might not have experience navigating the EHR and therefore wants to do a chart review but doesn't know where to go look for things.
Separate groups in org without a unified/efficient workflow - IRB, Data Governance, Team that can fulfill research data requests.
PIs may be able to access data but don't have the training to understand EHR Data
We use IT reports team for provisioning data to researchers. It includes access to chart review manually. IRB a must, including all in the research listed in the IRB
Some PIs may not have the knowledge to know what they need from the EHR or where they may find the Data in the EHR
PROCESS: Access is provisioned through HISARC (Health Information System Access Review Committee) which is a subcommittee of the HIPAA Oversight body at Ohio State. HISARC meets bi-monthly to triage requests for access. Requests are submitted via eServices (will be transitioning to REDCap in 2023). As part of triage, requests are verified for completion of requirements: drug screen, background check, IDP/HIPAA CBL, listed on protocol. Training is also required and verified prior to access.
A challenge with access is that they need IRB approval at some point and if they don't have a clear question it can be challenging. They often need an analyst to help them with understanding the data. They don't often have this kind of support to help answer the question. The question is usually broad and requires refinement. This takes additional resources and TIME. We have spent many hours helping investigators with refining their questions. Most groups may not have these resources.
Giving access to people not part of the covered entity
PIs may know they need IRB approval. There are groups that can help them but they may not be aware of these resources.

How do you make them aware they may be able to get data directly from the EHR via an honest broker rather than manual chart review?
We just transitioned to Epic, so the processes are being adjusted, but in general... Process: The researcher submits the request to either CTSI system or org ticketing system. Requests are triaged and reviewed to ensure all affiliation, regulatory and data sharing requirements are met. Analyst works with investigator to develop a data set for further analysis. This is an iterative process and can take several drafts. Challenges: transition to Epic puts this process at test; some researchers are better than others navigating reporting function to input parameters, and therefore may miss things; data transfer to the analysis software /redcap; not everyone follows the same process, rather follow what they used last, e.g. "let me email the same analyst!".
Managing access control is a separate process from IRB approval and the two systems don't talk to each other
How to improve data literacy across the institution
CHALLENGES/BARRIERS: Same form in eServices is used for requesting either clinical or research access. If requestor doesn't check the 'research' box, it delays processing. 'Business justification' is a required field on eServices form but it is vague, and requestors don't know what to put (e.g., "to complete job duties."). Requestors don't understand access levels (in-basket, view/read, full) Compounded by the way our eServices form is configured (they can check all types) ·Don't know how to access required dates (background check and/or drug screen) ·Approval of requestor's manager is required by eServices and if manager unavailable, delays process ·Capturing when a PI has credentials that put them into a specific category of access (Respiratory Therapist, Physical Therapist). ·Vaccination is a requirement when patient contact is involved but difficult to find details on what that entails (which vaccines are required). ·Requirement/renewal of drug screen ·Managing expectations – how long the process takes from request to access granted. Educating users to plan ahead. ·Training team and access triage activities are done by different people in different departments, coordination can be challenging (partially resolved with REDCap). Managing access from a compliance POV - making sure access approved aligns with access granted, training taken aligns with access granted, keeping up with changes in roles (e.g., when clinical role changes to research role) Educating requestors about IRB processes (e.g., waiver of consent), and coordinating with IRB on whether protocol is approved, key personnel, etc.
PIs, regardless of association with medical school or access to EHR must apply for access to EHR data for research through the Biomedical Informatics Core, which is part of the CTSA center. They also must have IRB approval. PIs are not allowed "interactive" access to our EHR system. All access is through the informatics core and Honest Broker system.
A researcher can take Epic training and gain access to Epic if they do not have access in a medical role. A researcher can pay for a data analytics to access the records for them, both methods require IRB permission
Access to the EMR doesn't convey understanding of the information or ability to navigate the EMR
IRB doesn't have authority to grant access to the EHR
PI may not know a chart review service exists
Access to EMR may require specialized training or certifications

Use Case 2: You have a person who is a clinician who is approved by the IRB to conduct a chart review.

One option we've taken: A designated group of persons can create a patient list in Epic (exporting from a Reporting Workbench or Slicer Dicer query with eligible patients), grant access to researcher to the patient list, then the researcher can do Chart Review w/o PHI leaving EHR
EMR audit and compliance flags inappropriate clinician access. This is incentive to work with IRB and CTSI informatics to request/log access for this research process
What approval process do you use for determining who has access?
Individuals who have access by virtue of their clinical role do not need to do anything additional for their access for research purposes. They do not go through the HISARC process.
There are policies they agree to regarding misuse of data, but only through auditing can we be certain they are accessing the right patients and data per the right IRB
Approval by IRB, Data Governance, and possibly Data Security Committee. You may have to specify the phenotype you want to look at.
Workflow exists to provide access for charts
The clinician will likely need help identifying the best set of records to review; this query can happen in Epic or in our RDW but each have pros/cons
We have discussed the idea of having a 'registry' for people using their clinical access for research purposes - our IRB/compliance folks like the idea but there is concern about getting adoption among busy clinicians
Is there/There is an assumption that access as a provider confers access as a researcher.
Do not even need IRB approval if they only need de-identified data. They can go the BMI Investigator and gain access.
Researchers might use tools such as TriNetX to develop a de-identified patient 'list' for research. No IRB approval needed. Then, if de-identification is requested, they get IRB approval and can complete their work in some cases.
Clinicians who are involved in research are usually familiar with chart review process but may need training on chart review SOP/guidelines so that it is consistent. This training may be needed to gain access once all other IRB requirements are met.
Often will require that the researcher obtain a list of "included" patients to narrow the patient focus of their chart review, e.g. only working from a list of patients with a specific diagnosis within a specified date range. This is often indicated by their research protocol.
They may need IRB approval for research chart review but the challenge is having the resources to analyze the data and to make sure it meets their needs. From previous experience an Investigator will perform chart review differently than a Study Coordinator. The Study Coordinator may follow a protocol but clinician will think in terms of patient care. It is a training issue.

Use Case 3: A PI hires a research coordinator to perform chart reviews.

<p>Challenge or Barrier: Researcher may not have EHR (Epic) login yet. They need this to do feasibility explorations e.g. with Slicer Dicer. We have a method (Epic CareLink) which can be used in some instances to give a person web-based access to only a specified subset of patients' charts</p>
<p>Adjusting the view</p>
<p>They will need somewhat overlapping trainings from campus and hospital. Hospital access requires additional permissions/appointments.</p>
<p>Yes, research coordinator can get access to charts after IRB and other approvals and training. Often the coordinators are internal to the PS's department/ division</p>
<p>None. For de-identified data they can just access the BMI Investigator.</p>
<p>PROCESS: Go through HISARC, can either be given view/read access or in-basket plus a variety of security templates (e.g., OBGYN).</p>
<p>We have a Research Academy for research professionals/coordinators that covers much of the processes and training required. This also raises awareness of expectations and policies.</p>
<p>Is the coordinator part of the covered entity? Do they have the appropriate training? If not same barrier as scenario #1 CRU at our institution has a coordinator core that will do this for research studies</p>
<p>CHALLENGES/BARRIERS: View/read gives more than minimum necessary in many cases. Coordinators may only need access to a subset of charts (e.g., based on clinic location OBGYN clinics). Looking to implement Slicer Dicer to limit access by location. • Distinction between access for research coordinators and study monitors. Study monitors have an entirely separate process not involving HISARC. • Determining when/if access should expire and monitoring expiration • Confusion over 'documentation' – distinction between recruitment/enrollment activities and writing in the research note • Additional use cases not defined by Research Coordinator role: Students (including Grad Students, PostDocs, fellows), Volunteers, Visiting Scholars, Interns, Research Contributor. Access for these roles varies widely and is highly case specific. Additional requirements may need to be met (e.g., Attestation and Confidentiality Agreement for scholars) • Disparity between options in eServices (e.g., job title) and requestor understanding of those options. Select "Student Research Assistant" but they are really a volunteer. • "model after" is a field in eServices that causes confusion (may be OSU specific) • Number of security templates is unwieldy and historical knowledge has been lost on the purpose of some of them. • An additional route could be in-basket with a list of MRNs being provided to our MIM team and they would push those charts to the in-basket. MIM is limited in resources so this is a constrained solution.</p>
<p>After IRB approval .For chart reviews for a research study we provide study specific training for identifying patients and for the data needed for the study. A QC and QA process is implemented to ensure there is consistency. If there are differences we discuss the reasons. This is used to help determine if they should continue access</p>
<p>Access to the EDW through report writers. Access to Epic is restricted.</p>
<p>Our Epic access has a role for CRCs specifically which gives them access to view "all" of the EHR and also enter orders and chart notes for research.</p>

Use Case 4: A PI hires a research coordinator to record research notes in the record.

CRCs have Epic access which allows them to view everything, document certain functions (RNs can actually chart medication administration if needed in some places), write notes, and enter research orders per protocol requirements using a customized order set for the study.
Would need some rudimentary Epic training. We don't have specific for research coordinators but can see value of that!
Issues are if not clearly "research note". May use a new qualitative test and record it in EMR, for example. Can be messy if not specifying research in advance or clearly in EMR
No writing access, only reading access! But can create, "Lists" of patients!
PROCESS: Go through HISARC, typically given full access.
None if they need de-identified data. They just go to the BMI Investigator. Writing back to the EHR is often done using FHIR put command. It can be a document or a message to the banner bar.
Research data cannot be entered in our EHR, only documentation if they are in a clinical trial, and this is done by the treating physician. This is my understanding anyway.
Research Coordinators can be granted access to consent patients identified by a phenotype. They are trained by their research group.
CHALLENGES/BARRIERS: ·Confusion over 'documentation' – distinction between recruitment/enrollment activities and writing in the research note
Coordinators can only enter "research notes"
At our institution Study Coordinators can request research access and editing in the medical record for documentation of screening and study visits
At our institution, this functionality (writing) for research notes is not available across studies. This is a mix of policy, practice and maturity of our EMR's research functionality. Main issue around this is discoverability.

Use Case 5: Are research coordinators part of the care team?

MUSC sometimes (it depends on study team, department, team make up)
They aren't handled that way here. We have a clear line between 'clinical' and 'research' Clinical uses are part of the covered entity. Research users from outside College of Medicine are not. Examples: College of Nursing, College of Public Health.
Challenges for UK- 1. Directions on obtaining direct access to data is unavailable to researchers 2. Recent move to Epic and full possibilities not operational 3. Require IRB for direct access but no one to review and approve that understands research 4. Participant recruitment requires physician with direct patient care or you can't contact patient which is why direct access is deterred. 5. CTSA extracts data for researchers instead of direct access currently.
YES
NO
UT Southwestern (sometimes)
Basic answer is NO, but in some cases they do become members of the care team.
During Epic research implementation we contemplated that research notes are not part of the patient history, it is clearly a "research note". Research Coordinator is not part of the care team.

Research requirements! Easier if part of the care team
Sometimes
UVA - sometimes
I don't think so, but actually not certain -Wake Forest
Sometimes. It depends on the study or funding. Study Coord as a service (resource core)...may not see patients. Study Coord part in aclinic may see patients.
VCU - sometimes
Not sure about this at Johns Hopkins

Use Case 6: What are the access requirements you impose on research users of your EHR?

CITI certification, and part of the university. Not aware of other requirements
For the team that we (in BMI) manage we require: Anyone hired has background check IRB training HIPAA training Information Security Training Listed on the honest broker team Other research or EMR training modules (job specific) Data Sharing /Data Governance overview
Drug screen Background check Institutional Data Policy (IDP)/HIPAA Training - annual Listed as key personnel on protocol Required training module(s) depending on what they will be doing
MUSC: General EHR access is not handled by the research informatics core. The research informatics core controls access to de-identified marts (e.g. i2b2 and TriNetX). For those, faculty have access by default. Others need faculty sponsors
Does the person have a Med Center ID? MedCenter Logon ID for person needing access Supervisor/Manager/Sponsor's name and MedCenter Logon ID (if not then via RIT) Required information Justification for level of access IRB protocol information: Added as key personnel or sub-investigator. Requires completion of CITI human subjects training. Requires completion of CITI responsible conduct of research (RCR) training. Requires completion of annual Conflicts of Interest disclosure (eCOI) OSU IRB protocol number, PI name and MedCenter Logon ID. Whether written HIPAA authorization is used Information on HIPAA waiver for written authorization (full, partial, none) Is the individual an undergraduate student, visiting scholar or non-OSU Medical Student Researcher Confidentiality Education Form and Personal Attestation signed by both the PI and the individual
Request for Research Access in REDCap
Validation of Completeness and Checklist Development Confirm all access
HISARC Review
Does HISARC approve?
Concerns identified and returned to the requestor
Requirements Not Met STOP
Two other types of IHIS access which get approval without HISARC: CareLink CTMO/CTO
Has to be done in eServices Could replace Excel spreadsheet with REDCap but point of entry is still eServices
Required Training OSUWMC Annual HIPAA Privacy and Security Training and date of completion (New requirement as of May 17, 2019) IHIS training will need to be completed before access is granted; however, we recommend submitting the request for access prior to completion of training. Does the Person require unattended access in the Medical Center Fingerprint background check (FBI/BCI) and

<p>date completed (must be done through OSU or OSUWMC) Will the person engage with research subjects on a face-to-face basis Vaccinations and date completed (if interacting with human subjects) Drug screening and date completed (to be removed***)</p>
<p>Most researchers do not have direct EHR access but instead access to our RDW. Direct EHR access for research is determined separately by the hospital and has different training and access requirements and regulatory oversight.</p>
<p>Approved</p>
<p>Complete Checklist</p>
<p>At VCU general research users are not allowed access to the EHR. They must go through the Informatics Core and have IRB approval for their requests. Researchers can have access to TriNetX through requesting an account through the informatics core (I do not think an IRB is required for this, just a vcu.edu account).</p>
<p>Does the individual have an OSUWMC account</p>
<p>Request Guest account via onboarding</p>
<p>Provision account via Information Security with appropriate access</p>
<p>EVERY employee goes through drug screen, background check, data protection training, plus more depending on role.</p>
<p>Requestor is notified</p>
<p>Researchers with IRB approval get access to i2b2/TriNetX/etc., but not directly to EHR</p>
<p>Individual is notified by requestor</p>

Appendix 2: Q&A Conversations

Question: After seeing the workflow posted, in some future iteration it would be interesting to see where do we align and where do we have differences across the different institutions. I thought that the responses, especially on some of the access questions were really interesting. It seems like we all are trying to figure it out ourselves, which of course is the whole point of why you're having this conversation.

Answer: Absolutely. And to be honest, one of the reasons why we're doing it this way is to allow everyone to be heard, and to also create a nexus around a conversation. [OSU] actually has very explicit decision rules about how you access the EHR. We have five different models for accessing the EHR, and we don't use Epic CareLink. We use Slicer Dicer integrated with Caboodle. So we use Caboodle to control Slice Dicer to limit the act. So we have a various technological access models.

Comment: I think that there are some institutions that have single points of contact for making some of these decisions. And there are other institutions that have data governance committees that collectively make these decisions. And I would like to understand how those function. And I like that strategy because different areas of expertise can really come together to make the best possible decisions. Whereas the single point of contact ones tend to make much narrower biased decisions because they're not that broader set of expertise. So I'd love to understand how those bodies function in that context.

Response: OSU has a governance body, the Health Information System Access Review Committee that does triage and adjudicate the request. However, there is one person on that committee that is the Chair of the committee and he really works very hard individually with each requester to [determine] exactly what their need is. And it takes a great deal of time. He spends a lot of time chasing down, especially visiting scholars and student researchers. He spends a lot of his time working with these requesters and figuring out exactly what they need and can they get by with Inbasket only. While we do have that governance model, we're also simultaneously kind of bound to an individual. And that's part of the process that Tim and I are trying to - can we build some decision rules that would take the place of that singular individual having to do that work.

Who makes the decision about who gets access?

When researchers are thinking of putting in grant submissions and they need to prove that a certain population exists at the institution to have enough 'n' to do the study, we used to use i2b2 to give us across the board data that anybody could have access and you could do searches to spit out that there are 158 cases in the EHR that gave you de-identified data. And then if your research proposal got approved you could go back to the IRB and then request that data so the research group could have permission to contact those patients.

At OSU, we're, we're actually exploring a third option which is Cosmos as an analog to i2b2, i.e. it is de-identified data. And now we use Cosmos which allows you to just look at your own institution as a filter. As a result, you can basically run queries using i2b2, you can run queries using Slicer Dicer in a web browser so you don't even have to give anyone access to the EHR. At OSU, they're very concerned about giving non-clinicians access to the direct access to the EHR. As an Epic shop have been very much bought into the Epic environment. We don't actually even have TriNetX and haven't gone down that road mostly because of politics related to concerns around providing pharmacy companies access to de-identify even the de-identified data.

Comment: I have an IRB specifically for researchers using TriNetX so they can go in and explore and build their cohort. If they want to use data beyond what exists inside of TriNetX, then they go and get their own IRB, whether it's de-identified or a limited data set, or a fully identified data set, and they're looking to recruit, or they're looking to do an identified retrospective study as well. We chose to go that way. We had been using i2b2, we'd been using a tool before that, and our i2b2 adoption was pretty scarce just because of the learning curve of the tool.

Question: So your experience with TriNetX has been primarily positive from the researcher's perspective?

Answer: From the researcher's perspective. This is not addressing the clinical trials that come in through TriNetX, but it really gives our faculty, staff and student with a mentor researchers, the opportunity to go in, look at the data, and understand that if they're making a request, data is coded. It better prepares them to come to our biomedical informatics team to ask questions and make larger data requests or data requests that are more complex than what you can get directly out of the tool.

Comment: I'm very interested in dynamic study specific research access.

Response: OSU is instituting it right now. We've tested it, but we're getting ready to deploy it. And once we do that, it's our intention to share it at XGM along with all of the code. We can have a research informaticist. It's really, it's really awesome. So the way it works is, if I want to give you full chart access to everyone in a department I can give it to you, I can assign security rules that give you access to a certain department, i.e. our OB GYN, you can just see the charts of everyone in that department. And so if I have a researcher in OB GYN who wants to do work, I can basically have research staff there, not a clinician, but their staff who need to go and have access to that, to go look for patients who are scheduled for appointments the next day, so that they know whether or not to go reach out to them. They can actually create reports in Slicer Dicer that allow them to basically create the inclusion criteria and then just rerun those appointments. And they get a list of everybody they should go talk to the next day.

Comment: That's great. Cause we haven't been able to do it at scale. We've done some things with views, like at the department level where we have departmental level analysts and we're trying to give them ability to do data driven management of their organizational unit. But without having everyone have access to everybody, which our auditors are nervous about, obviously, and then that's the way that's been difficult to scale beyond the department level. So what you're doing sounds really intriguing.

Response: So the other thing that we've figured out is a way to put the list of MRNs in Caboodle. So I have an informaticist write the list of MRNs. They have write access to Caboodle, they load it into caboodle. And then those people have access to that list of MRNs. And so they can use Slicer Dicer on that entire group. They can right click and go straight into the full chart. OSU will show any Epic team, one-on-one, what they have done.

Comment: Having been involved with providing data to researchers for the last 10 years, even before the Slicer Dicer was put in. So we used to use the BI tools to access the data from the backend and it's always a back and forth between the researchers and the informaticians. And as someone pointed out it's so critical that data literacy, those researchers, as well as the one was providing understand each other when it comes to all the different vocabularies, terminologies, ontologies, and all of that. So the other important aspect is did I as the informatician provide all the data that is there in the database to the researcher, did we miss some aspect of it because I did not include all the required codes for the search. So there are so many aspect. This is a vast domain, extremely vast domain. So we really need to pick and choose one specific scenario. And then engage everybody in that experience. So from those business intelligence tools to i2b2, I continuously use Slicer Dicer and now we are just moving into the OMOP data model with Atlas. So that's the one we are working now, as of now, it looks like this appears to be the best scenario because I can go back and forth to look at if I got all the patient the researchers needed or not using Atlas. It wasn't possible before. So there are various aspects to discuss, I think, just pick and choose one specific burning question and then involve everyone who have experience. And so that it's a learning experience for all involved.

Workshop Summary for Researcher Informatics

September 12, 2022

Collaborators:

Aaron J, Abajian M, Adams B, Adibuzzaman M, Anderson K, Baker M, Beno M, Burks S, Champion T, Cheng A, Cummins M, Dandamudi P, DiazGranados D, Ghosh A, Grudzinski J, Gupta L, Harper T, Harris K, Holden-Wiltse J, Huerta T, Kandpal M, Katoch A, Knosp B, Koepf B, Kolawole P, Laraway B, Nygaard J, Odden C, Paranal R, Pauli T, Pulgarin C, Rodgers L, Rojevsky S, Saroufim P, Sheng V, Song S, Tranelli K, Widmer K, Woods C, Wu W

Workshop Facilitator: Timothy Huerta, PHD, MS, Director, Biomedical Informatics, The Center for Clinical and Translational Services (CCTS) Chief Research Information Office (CRIO) and Associate Dean of Research Information Technology Professor, Biomedical Informatics and Family and Community Practice

Number of attendees: 40

Number of unique hubs attending: 25 hubs

Hub size of unique hubs: Small = 12, Medium = 3, Large = 8, Unsure = 2

Years of experience in Informatics of attendees: average years = 9.2; range = 0-30 years

Summary:

The goal of the Conversations Toward Solutions workshop was to give individuals a platform to discuss their challenges and experiences with research informatics. Listed below are the themes identified from qualitative analysis for each question.

Question 1: What tools do you have at your disposal to meet the demand for clinical data:

- Cross-organization data marts
- Citizen science
- Local EMRs and tools
- Common data models
- Survey/data management tools and software

Question 2: What are the implied set of skills that investigators are required to have to leverage summary and individual-level clinical data?

- Universal, scientist, clinical, informatics, data scientist and statistical skills

Question 3: From a technical and staffing perspective, what kind of resources, investments, and infrastructure are needed to support research informatics?

- Resources for payment
- Dedicated people for different roles
- Hardware

Question 4: How does your organization assess the impact/value of your clinical data access infrastructure?

- Usage, survey, and academic metrics

Participating Hubs:

- Boston University
- Case Western Reserve University
- George Washington University
- Medical University of South Carolina
- New York University - Langone
- Ohio State University
- Oregon Health & Science University
- Pennsylvania State University
- Rockefeller University
- Stanford University
- Tufts University
- University of California - Davis
- University of Colorado Denver
- University of Iowa
- University of Kentucky
- University of Miami
- University of Rochester
- University of Southern California
- University of Utah
- University of Virginia
- University of Wisconsin Madison
- Vanderbilt University
- Virginia Commonwealth University
- Wake Forest University
- Weill Medical College

Appendix 1: Workshop Discussions

Question 1: What tools do you have at your disposal to meet the demand for clinical data?

TrinetX, ACT, OMOP/ATLAS, RedCAP, Qlik, Business Objects
i2b2, TriNetX (NOT TRiNetX Research), OMOP, RedCap, Epic Slicer Dicer, Honest Broker from medical system research informatics, N3C as relevant,
TriNetX, Clinical Universe
OSU's List Deep6AI Cosmos SCARLET (a priori registry data delivery) i2b2/Shrine/ACT Slicer Dicer for Research Honest Broker (research informatics) Researcher access to Epic FHIR PCORNet LifeScale Data Lake Building an OPOP Data Warehouse Research Collaboratives - N3C, All of Us
OMOP EMERSE TriNetX Cosmos (Metro) Slicer Dicer
Slicer Dicer REDCap Qualtrics Research access to Epic Data Broker for custom queries -University of Miami
TriNetX, Metamorphosis, Emerse (future), reporting workbench, Epic Slicer/Dicer(future), PCORnet CDM, custom queries against EDW4R, Cosmos, N3C, Xnat, chart reviews, patient reported information -Boyd, Iowa
i2b2, SKAN-NLP, OMOP, data extraction from Clarity/Epic/Cerner
i2b2 for counts EHR Reporting for details OMOP (at SQL command line) for savvy investigators PCORnet for funded teams RECOVER for teams REDCap (with FHIR) ACT AoU N3C EMERSE (in planning) Qualtrics
For research summary counts 1) TriNetX, 2) Slicer Dicer 3) i2b2, all self-service. When patient-level data needed, then need to request data file via CTSI clinical data request process to clarify request and ensure protocol compliance. Variety of tools to fulfill patient-level data requests include Denodo views on EPIC sources and OMOP RDW. Coming soon EPIC Cosmos
TriNetX, ACT (i2b2/Shrine), N3C, local OMOP TRDW, Epic Slicer Dicer, and Cogito reports, REDCap Mark A., USC i2b2 for clinical data, and for counts only: TriNetX, plus 2 SHRINE networks
UCDH Slicer Dicer for counts Honest Broker (Clarity and Caboodle) Access to Epic OMOP BO REDCap i2b2 retired to use Slicer Dicer
Experiential training, unit data liasons, domain specific data marts -Boyd, Iowa
Trinetx, ACT, OMOP/ATLAS, RedCAP, Qlik, Business Objects
i2b2, TriNetX (NOT TRiNetX Research), OMOP, RedCap, Epic Slicer Dicer, Honest Broker from medical system research informatics, N3C as relevant,
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TriNetX, Metamorphosis, Emerse (future), reporting workbench, Epic Slicer/Dicer(future), PCORnet CDM, custom queries against EDW4R, Cosmos, N3C, Xnat, chart reviews, patient reported information -Boyd, Iowa

i2b2, SKAN-NLP, OMOP, data extraction from Clarity/Epic/Cerner

Question 2: What are the implied set of skills that investigators are required to have to leverage summary and individual-level clinical data?

Domain knowledge, dataset awareness (data dictionary document), compliance -HIPAA, privacy, IT security, data governance, study design, analytics. If they don't have these skills, we try to connect them with someone who does or provide access to training. All researchers asking for data start with TriNetX training (about 30 minutes). -Boyd, Iowa

Ideally you'd have both clinical familiarity with Epic and its data fields, and understanding of how to run a report. Informatics may lack clinical, and clinical may lack informatics skill

Basic understanding of digital phenotyping/ cohort selection, and ability to apply given a particular scientific question, interpretation of metadata/ data visualization, ability to proceed with study protocol given a relational database. Ability to validate data.

Slicer Dicer De-identified is self service; i2b2 must put in formal request through the SPARC Request system; no min level of expertise for identifiable data as their IRB approved research protocol would specify use

Workflows where the data is captured - How to validate data

There are many knowledge gaps. A huge challenge. Not resourced to address most of them. For self-service tools like TriNetx, it is use at your own (knowledge) risk

Domain knowledge

TriNetX, ACT - 1:1 trainings, Epic tools Epic requires training, REDCap - self-paced learning plus periodic workshops;

i2b2 - 30-minute introduction and then go on your own OMOP - SQL and domain expertise REDCap – none

We need to meet investigators where they are - there is no one-size fits all solution

OSU requires specific tool knowledge, but we are also currently heavily reliant on our honest broker process to deliver concierge-based approaches to data abstraction. We are moving to standardize that process in the future through OMOP (as an example). For example, we have an Azure data lake product to support AI/ML loads but that requires that the research team have someone that understands how to use those kinds of tools (e.g., Data Bricks) We are toying with Cosmos/Slicer Dicer for cohort selection and then running those reports to deliver data.... we have a new Epic row level tool for doing chart abstractions.

Our goal is to create tools for use by research teams, limiting as much as possible the need for them to rely on informatics support to pull clinical data. Much of our training/education is increasingly focused on providing end users with the knowledge in not only how to use the tools, but to understand key considerations when querying clinical data to ensure what they want to know, and how they query it, are aligned.

Consideration: At what level of access? - Researchers using a self-service tool have a different level of skills -than someone accessing clinical (e.g. Epic Clarity or Caboodle) data via SQL -than someone accessing a derived dataset (e.g. OMOP or PCORnet CDM) via SQL or SAS or R. -Boyd

Implied skills = initially assume that users know nothing about the data (but definitely think that what they want will be easy and completely clean)

Question 3: From a technical and staffing perspective, what kind of resources, investments, and infrastructure are needed to support research informatics?

<p>We charge for labor - \$125/hour. We also offer a subscription service option - monthly fee per project. We prefer getting %FTE funded on grants. All subsidized by institution \$ -Iowa</p>
<p>We have two data scientists for AI/ML side, a large team with ETL, Architect/analysts for loading/refreshing. Programmers for front end side and then two honest data brokers.</p>
<p>Staffing 1. Researcher facing analysts 2. Data facing query and ETL staff - DBAs 3. Faculty mentors/data liaisons -not CTSA 4. Staff data liaisons - not CTSA 4. Faculty science leads 5. Staff management leads 6. Project management 7. Clinical IT team members 8. REDCap team - 2 analysts and a sys admin. 9. Biosample Information System team 10. App dev team -Iowa</p>
<p>Institutional subsidy largely covers staff costs. CTSA and other grants cover substantially smaller portions. Chargebacks to investigators (up to \$50k) comprise the rest. Chargebacks help ensure investigators have "skin in the game" and attend meetings. We lack staff to address current demand. Adding staff is challenging given global labor shortage, competition from industry, and nuance to succeed in AMCs/informatics. Onboarding new staff takes 12 months. Activation energy is high. When we increase capacity, demand immediately consumes it. This is not sustainable.</p>
<p>Infrastructure: 1. Database server(s) 2. Virtual server resources for application and project storage 3. REDCap server 4. HIPAA compliant storage for data extracts 5. Data enclave with access to HPC resources 6. Collaborative resources (e.g. MS Teams). 7. Space in Healthcare datacenter -Iowa</p>
<p>OSU Approach 1. Researcher facing analysts (\$104 an hour) act as Staff data liaisons (the CTSA provides vouchers up to 3000 to cover data access costs) 2. Data facing query and ETL staff - DBAs 3. Working on establishing resource ambassadors to cover infrastructure across the biomedical mission OSU has a \$2.5M investment in Research IT through the CRIO annually, which is augmented by \$500K from our CTSA. Our RIT infrastructure has a budget of about 4.5M that includes projects that are funded by grants and include UX/UI/Design, Data Science as a Service (that includes Informatics), Electronic Data Capture (REDCap/Qualtrics) and Software Development (I have about 15 people in this group working on projects supporting grants and the greater good)</p>
<p>REDCap development - SOW and fee for funded projects, free for non-funded projects; 30 min consultation is free. Fee is a blended rate of all type of staff potentially supporting this. There are levels/tiers Data related: -Cohort discovery (aggregated counts) free of charge, usually it is a low effort. Data extraction - currently free, plan is to move towards fee for service solution, ML/AI is for funded projects and fee-based. Staff availability is always an issue, spread too thin between many projects</p>
<p>At a very basic level, one thing we need is an enterprise-wide de-identification resource. First cut would be verification that 18 HIPAA identifiers are removed, but of course there may be more analysis required based on "indirect identifiers"</p>
<p>Data science service with analysts/ concierge service + BMIC team that facilitates expedited data access via use of self-service TriNetX Cohort selection. Mix of institutional/ CTSA funding/ chargeback. HIPAA protected environments for high performance computing. REDCAP for delivering data in an analysis-friendly platform. We charge \$95/ hour for informatics services, with some free time for students.</p>

There needs to be a business case at some level. We offer fee for service for CDW analysts (\$100/hr) directly accessing data. For our Common Data Model work (OMOP/i2b2) it tends to be effort support on a project by project basis.

Question 4: How does your organization assess the impact/value of your clinical data access infrastructure?

Papers Grants Usage

Two angles: Utilization and outcomes. Service/resource utilization - numbers of... and slice it various ways) Project impact/outcomes: Publications, presentations, funding applications... The bottom line - did we contribute to the success? When we get to the point of individual access, we will be assessing the number of independent users.

Service stats - number of studies, number of users #publications - something that is tracked for all faculty. #grant applications supported #funded grants supported \$coming into BMI Core -Iowa

Metrics and ROI are not clearly defined but include: Grants - applications and funded Papers, abstracts, talks locally and nationally. Amount of training provided to researchers. Number of consults beyond training Medical students trained on informatics tools Number of collaborations that span departments, schools, and institutions

Grant \$ - pubs - program self-sufficiency (lack of need for supplemental funding) - productivity in priority research domains (for us health equity) - query counts - consultation hours - satisfaction surveys

We currently use standard measures like utilization, grants, and dissemination outcomes. Moving to RE-AIM framework that encompasses these and other measures.

OSU measures the number of requests, number of CTSA-supported articles and grant expenditures. In the new application, we are moving towards a RE-AIM based framework for evaluation. I wish we had a better way to track papers - we have a big issue with acknowledgement by endusers of CTSA investments.

Question 5: Based on your experience, what guidance might you for a University that was setting up clinical data access for research?

For an under-resourced institution, go all in with TriNetX to go fast. For a well-resourced institution, implement incrementally-refreshed OMOP and train biostatisticians to run queries on behalf of investigators. Use OMOP to enable TriNetX for investigators with low technical skills and OMOP SQL for those with high technical skills. Setup REDCap with FHIR. Define process and governance.

For Universities that do not own the hospital, seek out another University that has already figured it out (or at least seems to have figured it out) - don't try to reinvent the wheel. Ensure that the decision makers/funders actually have a clear vision of what they want to accomplish. Require that all potential users of clinical data for research have some core competencies around the data (this goes beyond taking some online HIPAA courses and being "credentialed" for research. Data being extracted and delivered needs to be cleaned first, otherwise research will be done that leads to erroneous conclusions, and possible downstream harm to patients

Review current state and identify gaps to prioritize for development: Assess level of data governance - who owns the data, what agreements are in place and what are needed. Who makes decisions about the use of clinical data for research? Resource review - what staffing and tools are available

now and what gaps are there for researchers wanting to access the data. Community engagement - Who wants to use this data and what are their needs? Connect with enterprise IT (both Healthcare and Institutional IT) and explore their interest and resources for partnering in delivering data to researchers. Connect with IRB and Compliance office, as well as security.

Meet researchers where they are to support the full spectrum of skills and use cases. - provide expert analytics services for direct EHR extraction and consultation - support at least one Common Data Model to support self-service queries, national collaborations, and shared code - Show value by spreading successful project - Leverage the work of others (many on this call) to save money and increase efficiency - be patient, these things take time

Perform needs assessment first. Explore what can be re-used/augmented to serve another purpose, rather than starting anew as if nothing exists. Then build new and better. Train the trainer. Centralizing and holding expertise too close results on resource deficit :)

Workshop Summary for Health Information Exchanges

October 17, 2022

Collaborators:

Barbour E, Brown J, Cramer B, Cummins M, Holden-Wiltse J, Hopmeier H, Huerta T, Koepf B, Lawrence J, Mahmood F, Obeid j, Ostasiewski B, Quinn T, Rodgers L, Rojevsky S, Sagiraju S, Talbert J, Walker C, Woods, C

Workshop Facilitator: Timothy Huerta, PHD, MS, Director, Biomedical Informatics, The Center for Clinical and Translational Services (CCTS) Chief Research Information Office (CRIO) and Associate Dean of Research Information Technology Professor, Biomedical Informatics and Family and Community Practice

Number of attendees: 19

Number of unique hubs attending: 13 hubs

Hub size of unique hubs: Small = 6, Medium = 4, Large = 2, Unsure = 1

Years of experience in Informatics of attendees: average years = 9.8; range = 0-22 years

Summary:

The goal of the Conversations Toward Solutions workshop was to give individuals a platform to discuss their challenges and experiences with health information exchanges. Listed below are the themes identified from qualitative analysis of the workshop transcript.

Types of health information exchanges used:

Clinical care:

- Care Everywhere

Research:

- Shrine
- Epic Clinical trials
- Tools that allow for cohort identification across multiple sites
- All of Us
- I2b2 Shrine
- PCORNet
- Registries
- TriNetx
- Claims Data

Infrastructure:

- How do you manage external records requests?
- Are there external records requests?
- How do you secure clinical experience data from other sites?
- How is consent managed at your organization and across organizations?

Data Origin:

- Internal
- External
 - How do you manage patients and patient data that don't come from your institution?
 - Federated Healthcare Org to Healthcare Org Transfer (Care Everywhere)
- The patient
- Research
- Sometimes research is at the nexus of research in clinical care, in clinical trials, that's the case.
- Registries are a source of research data.

Data used for/by

- Internal purposes
- External purposes
- The patient
- Research
 - Phase 1 clinical trials where individuals in the trial aren't patients of the institution where the trial is occurring.
 - What does the workflow for securing clinical data from your site look like when you're participating in a multi-site study where you are not the central hub?

Mode of data collection:

- API
- FHIR
- Fax
- Manual data requests

Data from external sources:

- Care Everywhere is not ingressed into the EMR discretely.
- Data from outside of the organization is good enough for research
- Data from outside the organization is not good enough for clinical care

What data can be used for what purpose?

- Using Care Everywhere to request data for research is not allowed except for public health emergencies.
- Care Everywhere is used to transfer data for research.

How do you get healthcare data when there is no universal format for healthcare data?

- Community primary care clinics and we asked them to give us effectively eight variables out of their EHR, and they couldn't with any level of fidelity
- Mapping and data transfer are two separate problems.

Participating Hubs:

- Case Western Reserve University
- Icahn School of Medicine at Mt. Sinai
- Medical University of South Carolina
- Ohio State University
- Tufts University
- University of California – Davis
- University of Illinois at Chicago
- University of Kentucky
- University of Rochester
- University of Texas at Galveston
- University of Utah
- Virginia Commonwealth University
- Wake Forest University

Appendix 1: Workshop Discussions

Question 1: When researchers are asking for either summary and/or individual-level clinical data...how does your organization treat data from other organizations when your researchers are asking for data?

Is there a common data model in use with standards where interpretation can be more trusted
Respond with questions: Who is asking for data? What data are they asking for? Data classification
What do they plan to do with the data? (view, share, etc.) How will they access the data?

Question 2: When researchers are asking for either summary and/or individual-level clinical data...what does the workflow for securing clinical data from your site look like when you are participating in a multi-site study where you are not the central hub? If you have been a central hub, what are the diversity of approaches that you have used/seen used in data delivery?

What are the data? Where are the data currently stored? And in what format? How can we transfer the data? How will the hub receive the data? What security measures do we need to ensure before releasing the data? How do we confirm the data were received when it leaves our site?

Question 3: When researchers are asking for either summary and/or individual-level clinical data... what has your experience, if any, been in engaging with community sites outside of your healthcare system with regard to participation in research and associated data transfer

Willingness to share information or make information available through agreed upon mechanism
Dedicated people for different roles
Hardware

Question 4: When researchers are asking for either summary and/or individual-level clinical data... What tools do you use to support cohort identification? What are their pros and cons?

Epic Clinical Trials
TrinetX
You can form private networks with other user sites and query cohort numbers across those sites - this is separate from industry use of the network
AllofUs
N3C
Secure workspace accessible to all who are approved based on established governance, can run more advanced analysis on row level data
PCORNet (including PEDSNet)
i2b2/SHRINE/ ACT
Have to define and map to an agreed upon ontology with other sites, easy to then run cohort counts only
ACT/ENACT is one example of a SHRINE network
More involved an onboarding process - only with approved project, no general querying
Individual sites choose if they want to participate in any given query/project
Usage, survey, and academic metrics

Question 5: Based on your experience, what guidance might you have for a University that was setting up health information exchange for research?

Engage clinicians in help mapping to standards/ concepts -Brian O

<https://i2b2transmart.org/>

If you are a TriNetX member, they help with mapping and do a good job.

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